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INSTRUMENTI PRAVNE ZAŠTITE DECE U GRAĐANSKOM ZAKONIKU KNEŽEVINE SRBIJE IZ 1844. GODINE

Srpski građanski zakonik, usvojen 6. aprila 1844. godine, predstavlja prvi pokušaj kodifikovanog pristupa pravne zaštite dece u modernoj srpskoj državi. Premda ovaj Zakonik ne poznaje savremeni koncept „prava deteta“, njegova struktura i brojna rešenja predstavljaju ranu formu institucionalne brige o maloletnim licima, zasnovanu na kombinaciji porodičnopravnih, naslednopravnih i obligacionopravnih normi. Autori će kroz ovaj rad izvršiti analizu ključnih mehanizma zaštite, među kojima posebno mesto zauzima institut starateljstva, zasnovan na principu da odraslo lice, određeno od strane vlasti ili porodice, preuzima pravnu odgovornost za dete koje nije sposobno da samostalno upravlja svojim pravima i obavezama. Zakonikom se precizno uređuje imovinska zaštita maloletnika, propisujući dužnost staratelja da upravlja imovinom deteta, uz nadzor nadležnih organa, kao i stroga ograničenja raspolaganja tom imovinom. Time se obezbeđuje zaštita ekonomskih interesa deteta od zloupotreba, ali i od nepromišljenih pravnih radnji. Ovaj deo zakonika, koji je govorio o institutu starateljstva, kasnije 1872. godine je zamenjen Zakonom o starateljstvu, ali su njegova prvobitna normativna rešenja bitno uticala na tekst novog zakona. Poseban segment rada posvetiće se analizi poglavlja o pravima i dužnostima roditelja, koje je u Zakoniku shvaćeno kao skup ovlašćenja i dužnosti usmerenih na zaštitu deteta, uključujući obavezu izdržavanja i obezbeđivanja adekvatnog vaspitanja. Izvršiće se analiza i rešenja koja se odnose na vanbračnu decu, čiji je pravni položaj bio strogo određen, ali ipak i regulisan određenim vidovima zaštite, naročito u pogledu izdržavanja i ograničenog nasleđivanja. Cilj ovog rada biće da se utvrdi u kojoj meri je Zakonik iz 1844. godine predstavljao napredak u institucionalizaciji mera zaštite dece, kao i to da istraži kako su njegova rešenja doprinela kasnijem razvoju domaćeg porodičnog prava i modernih metoda zaštite prava deteta.

Ključne reči: Srpski građanski zakonik, Kneževina Srbija, prava deteta, porodično pravo, zaštita, dete.

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INSTRUMENTS OF LEGAL PROTECTION OF CHILDREN IN THE CIVIL CODE OF THE PRINCIPALITY OF SERBIA FROM 1844

The Civil Code the Principality of Serbia, adopted on 6 April 1844, was the first attempt at a codified approach to the legal protection of children in the modern Serbian state. Although this Code did not recognize the contemporary concept of "child rights", its structure and numerous legal solutions represent an early form of institutional care for minors, based on a combination of family law, inheritance law, and obligation law norms. In this paper, the authors analyze the key protection mechanisms envisaged in this Code. The most prominent among them is the institute of guardianship, which is based on the principle that an adult, appointed by the authorities or the family, assumes legal responsibility for a child who is unable to independently manage his/her rights and obligations. The Code precisely regulates the property protection of minors, prescribing the duty of the guardian to manage the child's property under the supervision of the competent authorities, as well as strict restrictions on the disposition of that property. This ensures the protection of the child's economic interests from abuse but also from reckless legal actions. The part of the Code which regulated the institution of guardianship was later replaced by the Guardianship Act (in 1872), but its original normative solutions significantly influenced the text of the new law. In a separate section of the paper, the authors analyze the Code provisions (chapter) on the rights and duties of parents, which are perceived as a set of powers and duties aimed at protecting the child, including the obligation to support and ensure adequate upbringing. The authors also analyze the legal solutions relating to illegitimate children, whose legal status was strictly defined but still regulated by certain types of protection, particularly in terms of child support and limited inheritance. The goal of this paper is to determine to what extent the Civil Code of 1844 contributed to the development in the institutionalization of child protection measures, as well as to explore how its solutions contributed to the later development of domestic family law and modern methods of children's rights protection.

Keywords: Civil Code 1844, Principality of Serbia, family law, children's rights protection.